

Applications of dimedone in the synthesis of heterocycles: An update

[Majid M. Heravi](#)¹, Vahideh Zadsirjan, Bahareh Fattahi, Niousha Nazari

¹ Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Physics & Chemistry Alzahra University, Vanak, Tehran, Iran.

Abstract

Dimedone (5,5-dimethylcyclohexane-1,3-dione) is an alicyclic diketone, occasionally considered as building blocks in design and synthesis of a wide variety of heterocycles. The synthetic efficacy of dimedone as a synthon has been presented as a chapter in *Advances in Heterocyclic Chemistry* in 2009. Due to importance of dimedone and huge numbers of cited references concerning its applications after 2009 till date, in this review we try to update its unique role as a privileged synthon in the synthesis of different heterocyclic compounds.

Keywords

Alicyclic diketone, Dimedone, Heterocycles, Multicomponent reaction